

The Participation of Citizens in Planning Public Policy in Vietnam

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Abstract:

When studying the issue of citizen participation in public policies of the state, there is a problem that the level of participation of the people is limited. Although the constitution stipulates recognized Vietnamese citizens have the right to participate in state and social management, participate in the discussion of common issues of the whole country and the locality, to petition the housing authorities. Country, voting when the State organizes a referendum. The following article will further analyze this issue

Keywords: Citizens, public policy, Vietnam

1. Introduction

Vietnam is in the transition from traditional society to modern democratic society. Currently, Vietnamese's State has been highly considered to promote citizen participation in planning and policy issues of national importance.

Depending on which historical period the level of participation of the people on economic issues - politics in Vietnam is also different. There have been periods contribute to people's opinions are not respected, which is the period before 1986, the mechanism of bureaucratic, centralized subsidy has not promoted the strength of the people. State policies also impose no realistic calculation has therefore created dependence, the passivity of the people expects, Vietnam delays in development.

During the renovation period, the Party and State have made great efforts to expand democracy and promote collective ownership of people, enabling more people to participate in the management of the country. The participation of citizens in economic life - society is increasingly aware and more fully correct. Citizens are involved from the planning, implementation to monitoring and evaluation results.

2. The equal acceptance level of citizens in Vietnam

First of all, a Democratic State ruled by law, to obey the law, but not only that democracy is the desired state and promote the rights of the citizen. In Vietnam, despite the implementation of this level is not perfect but there are certain steps, enabling citizens can contribute their opinions on important matters of the country.

2.1. Level of equal acceptance

During periods of equal rights in Vietnam have been increasingly developed and concretized in the constitution: in 1946, 1959, 1980, 1992 and amended in 2001 and other legal documents State: Election Law, the Law on denunciations and complaints, Labor Law, Law on Gender Equality, Law on Social Insurance, Health Insurance Law ... and in the international conventions which Vietnam has signed.

Acceptable level of equality of citizens in Vietnam through different periods of history is different. Since the State Democratic Republic of Vietnam was established residents are entitled to equal rights, this content is confirmed in the Constitution and other legal documents.

There are two questions; one is why the participation is not uniform like that? Question two: the politics like?

2.2. The cause of the acceptance of unequal

In essence, people are independent individuals, not equal (with the stronger, more intelligent a person ...)

Historical factors: the years before the renovation period (1986), Vietnam during the centralized bureaucratic economy, collectivization, nationalization. During this period, all people accept inequality as a factor, of course, all benefits are equal, and people just focus on advocacy issues on mass media without the attention to the real issues. People of Vietnam in this period generally accepted the nature of the conflict rather than conflict silent public...

Elements of religion, ideologies: Vietnam under Confucian Orient: common issues of interest to the immediate interests and practical of the people themselves should limit participation in political life. At the same time influenced by Buddhist people afraid to debate, have you thought of catabolism, did not dare to fight...

Social - Economic factors: groups living in different conditions to the development of uneven economic, educational level differences between nations, regions. Kinh ethnic economic life, educational level higher development and other

ethnic groups because of favorable living conditions, while ethnic minorities have lower economic because they live in more difficult conditions.

2.3. Political impact

To the period after 1986, the participation of citizens and expand more in political life. However, the feedback received by the State before the problems that citizens have limited sets did not meet their expectations. There are cases where their opinions fall into silence so that their participation is not effective, so many times forms the ideological indifference. People usually only interested in the immediate interests of itself, the benefits are less common interest.

State is a collection of political leaders, administrative and civil servants. Do the leadership and employees are ready to open with the requirements of the people or not? The answer is: Not all are open attitude, this has impacted people. When people feel heard, they will be reflected in two ways: reactive (negative): World City, indifference or apathy ... Example: In Vietnam, so people can see the indifference of citizens to political activities of the State. According to psychologists, the social is normal, people just dedicated to somewhere when their opinions are valued and attention. They think that I only invest when the time is useful or can do something to change. If I do not organize them to take or seek to World City, do not fight. The main church in attitude that has made the absurd policy cannot effectively exist in a long time.

State of Vietnam has many mechanisms to support the economic, health care and education for disadvantaged groups, less developed in society (women, poor, disabled, ethnic minorities) to these groups have more opportunity to participate. But in fact, this support is not enough for them to participate equally in the political life of the country. In a democratic society, to achieve equality, the need to struggle, must plan, considering it as a project to strive to do. That is why regional differences, ethnic, religion, level of awareness ... should always be a certain distance to the right of equality, the question is how to bridge the gap of inequality that most effectively.

Due to the impact of the globalization process, in Vietnam people's demands will increase in the coming years. This is a normal phenomenon, how important is the control process of the people involved. The participation of the people is likely to be demonstrations on the streets to demand their rights or group of them. The average equity is a virus, washed into each person, how can control to not fall into chaos, the State should develop better policies to be able to collect, handle the requirements and demands of the people fully effective. A society where people do not really participate in equal society will lead to that state not to mobilize the collective strength, the gray matter impoverished, underdeveloped and slow innovation. This poses a challenge for Vietnam in the period of complete democracy in the international integration trend.

3. The participation of citizens in planning public policy

3.1. Democratic state and the right to participate in policy-making of citizens

A democratic state is a state where people have ownership, the fundamental rights of citizens are respected, protected. Besides, for a modern democratic state, the institutions of state also enabling people to participate in the election process representations, participation in construction law, social policy as well as an operator performing the review of social, express their views, contribute to creating a truly democratic society, public and transparent.

State of Vietnam since its establishment in 1945 until now always towards a modern democratic state, which in addition to respecting the fundamental rights of citizens as political rights, civil, economic, cultural and social goods, and the State wishes to promote the power of the people, enabling people to participate in political life in general and the legislative process, public policy in particular. The participation of citizens in the life of Vietnam civil society, the policy is legal in Vietnam recorded many constitutional and other legal documents. Specifically, the 53 provisions of the Constitution: "Citizens have the right to Vietnam to participate in State and social management, to discuss common issues of national and local proposals to state agencies, said decide when the referendum. " 1992 Constitution: "Citizens exercising their ownership at the grassroots level by participating in the work of state institutions and social and public life."

Thus, the participation of citizens in policy making process in Vietnam has been the Constitution specifies. Decision-making process of state agencies, the agency's request the people's representatives to listen and communicate people's opinions on policy issues and legislation are also provisions in a number of legal documents Other laws such as the National Assembly Election Law, Law on Election of People's Council at all levels, Civil Law, Law on civil servants, the Law on Complaints and denunciations.

The participation of citizens in the process of making public policy expressed by the following three basic forms: Indirect election through the National Assembly, the highest representative body for powerful people and the People's

Council is the body representing the highest power in the local people. National Assembly delegates with voters, listen to their opinions and aspirations of the people to reflect the government to promptly take the appropriate policy changes. On the other hand, the National Assembly also represents the people through the bills, the economic development strategy - the National Socialist and many other important policies. Based on the opinions of people on issues arising in society, the complaints and denunciations, the question session (live broadcast), the representations of people reflecting government agencies to respond to people or timely policy adjustments, including the content were submitted to the National Assembly for consideration and amendment of legal documents involved.

Direct: citizen participation comments on draft Bills, written under the law through mass media like newspapers, radio, the Internet, through organizations like the Women's Social, Lawyers' Association, Veterans Association, a trade union organization, the Fatherland Front ... This is the forum, a common space for people to directly express opinions, voice their state, can be agreed or disagreed with the problems that the State is expected to institutionalize the legal documents.

Reflecting society: the law of Vietnam also stipulated the right of the people in the feedback and complaints issues were State provisions into law, but the law enforcement to implementation or improper implementation, affecting people's interests. At the same time, people have the right to propose practical issues arising in social life to improve policy through a written petition submitted to the authorities. Through the questioning session of the National Assembly, the People's Council, people reflect what the problem is for the hot-pressing in society are, on the basis that the State agencies to acquire and edit suitable for practice.

Overall assessment: The participation of citizens in the policy-making process of law is extremely important. Different periods and periods of history, which involved a much more active and extensive, effective for the policymakers as well as creating conditions for people to promote their own interests and contribute renovation of state management mechanism. Practice shows that much major policy of the State plan in place, but when discussed publicly, people have positive comments, evaluate the impact of such policies and those policies that not match reality, so the State has promptly reviewed.

However, there exist some problems, such as:

First, the sense of responsibility of the people is not high due to a limited degree about-face, indifferent attitudes do not care, that the policy-making, lawmaking is the State agency, or if they participate in natural forms and watered. On the other hand, the political culture of the people still not high, not equal due to historical, traditional elements, habits ... while the State is not giving them a wide public space and not providing give them sufficient tools and means they are willing to participate.

Secondly, people usually pay much attention to the issues in detail, in particular where they live as land issues, housing construction, urban transport, the environment, but little attention to the issues Overall, issues related to institutional and national strategies or to participate but not high performance.

Thirdly, the participation of citizens through social critics (petitions, complaints, and denunciations) is the main form. When the policy launched direct impact to people, they respond to new policies that do not participate as soon as the State is developing a draft and get comments because they think that policy is not whether or not related to her.

Fourthly, absorbing the quality of citizens' opinions to what extent depends on the qualifications and competence of staff and building public policy and law enforcement involved. In fact, many comments from citizens were in the process of acquiring and building a complete legal system, but not comprehensive and widespread. Many people pose problems not receive or accept a limited, not fully evaluated, comprehensive or ignored, leading to the implementation of policies more difficult, does not meet practical requirements, not the people responding (e.g. delete provisions about tricycles, self-made vehicles in urban areas while it is mainly the means of livelihood of poor urban classes, no positive measures on employment, financial support for them; or regulations on traffic flow distribution in Hanoi and Ho Chi Minh City does not match reality ...).

Fifthly, should improve the system of policies and laws on the basis of provisions specifically and comprehensively on issues related to the expansion of democratic rights of the people, more specific provisions of the and content so that people can freely express their voice, to the State's policies closer to life.

3.2. Openness, transparency, and quality of public discussion

State of Vietnam has made great efforts to publicize, transparency in the formulation and implementation of legislation, public policy and has achieved certain results as public questioning sessions Government of Deputies, live broadcast of the dialogue between government, business and people on the social issues are concerned. The bodies of State power, as well as central provinces, have held more people regularly, so people are directly meet and exchange a

democratic, more frank with state agencies. Many forums have been created so that people can contribute ideas, express their aspirations, as the meeting point of communes, wards, newspaper and TV media, the Internet, television (near it held more of the live broadcast to discuss hot issues that public opinion is concerned) or through political organizations, social and mass organizations to exchange, reflect social Assembly input to state agencies. Many projects have the scope Law broad, affecting many people's lives to be printed in newspapers, on internets to consultation of the people, the people responded positively.

However, the participation of citizens in policy making has not been done thoroughly and efficiently, many issues have not been set by competent agencies solved as management issues Land in urban areas, traffic management, urban planning, issues to promote democracy at the grassroots was not really democratic or anti-corruption issues ... There are issues that the state has no opinion clear and specific as the plan should establish independent trade unions or not, the issue of freedom of association, freedom of establishment of private TV companies ... There are many diverse forums, extensive open public space, environment or provide adequate tools and means for citizens to freely express opinions, which may be multidimensional and goes against the views of the State.

3.3. Relations between the State and interest groups

Currently, different interest groups in society to participate more actively in the democratic process, to effect greater social and economic life, certain influence to the operation of the State, contributing promote the development of society.

In the opinion of Jeffrey Berry, "the Association of the interest groups' interests is a group of organized structure of citizens who have common goals and want to influence public policy". There are two kinds of Interest group: public interest groups, advocating for the interests of some shareholders or society as assemblies, environmental protection, labor unions, farmers, etc... and private interest groups, campaigning for the interests only local interests of a very small number of members (as in a business demanding protection for their industries, etc.).

The private interest groups, with greater financial strength and in the adjacent armpit with the State, it evolved and adapted to the economic growth faster than the perception of the general public, or interest groups public. No doubt, private interest groups in Vietnam will be growing, increasingly deep intervention into the policy process. If the State does not recognize early and prepare to live with it, these private interest groups can block reforms or reform process slid out of control, creating a society dominated by a minority.

So to solve this problem, absolutely not trying to prevent that is to create a roadmap to our benefit to society and to accelerate reform. If a legal framework for lobbying activities (Lobby) and the transparency policy, interest groups will have to persuade and mobilize public investment rather than officials.

In the environment lack of transparency, the holes in the mechanism are where the interest groups to gain a spin. For example, the controlling mechanism for businesses, schools, create interest groups located in the state apparatus and has intimate relations with the public authorities. Policymaking process is not transparent (lack of information to evaluate the impact of social groups) will provide an opportunity "black deal" of some interest groups with officials.

The solution to harmonize interest groups:

Firstly, we have to create mechanisms to control the power between private interest groups. The competition among rival interest groups will have reduced the attack on the policymakers. For example, in automotive protection policy, an association of car importers (new and old) will create a balance in the automobile industry development policy.

Secondly, we have to condition the interests of public interest groups. To ensure that each policy in the future truly represents the interests of the majority, necessary to create conditions for the formation of interest groups. Indeed there were signs of a breakthrough when the government assigned to the Union of the scientific and technical draft law on associations.

To make things more benefits, the State should have regulations to promote the link between voters by interest groups: The link was made through centralized institutions such as the Fatherland Front, the union. However, besides the political advantages of these organizations for the spirit of national unity, the political activities of these organizations reveal many limitations in the market economy have all the benefits mix and counterclockwise. So we need to create a legal environment for the establishment of assembly and operation of associations, facilitating the association of citizens according to interest groups. It would be defined in order to balance the interests and ensure a harmonious social development. However, it is necessary to have regulations on lobbying, publicity and transparency in lobbying to prevent the impact of these groups have opposing interests, ensuring the cooperation of a healthy social Civil Assembly. It should also set rules to control these organizations, individuals, and associations active in the field of

professional activity and to distinguish this operation with the voluntary contributions of citizens in the legislative process.

In practice, the State has made great efforts to meet the requirements set on the basis of ensuring harmony between different interest groups, protect the interests between the parties, the State's interests and rights of citizens, promote social development.

3.4. Issue of implementing democracy in the process of policy making in Vietnam

As analyzed above, the participation of citizens planning the process of public policy through the forms directly, indirectly or through social critics, performing the inspection and monitoring has shown democracy of the modern democratic state. To analyze in more detail about the process of direct democracy, the scope of this article refers to some basic issues:

Referendum: The process of direct democracy is a process that allows citizens to mobilize jointly decide that a problem in the country. Present implementation issues referendum as prescribed by the Constitution, but the fact this power of the people is rarely used, partly because of the political culture of Vietnam, educational level, or attitude apathy, not interest. However, in the recent National Assembly session, many delegates said that the Government and Parliament should have clearly defined, specific and active in the referendum. It is also a manifestation of direct democracy.

Currently, the Government has conducted opinion directly contribute to some people's draft through the Internet using E-democracy as the Land Law.

Legislative initiatives: It is the people making recommendations to Congress on the development and promulgation of legal documents. For example, the State opened the forums (which are considered a public space) so that people can participate in policy initiatives on issues such as environment, housing, construction, urban planning...

Election and dismissal: The election of deputies to the National Assembly and the Council of People's Assembly passed a resolution and dismissal, dismissal of titles by the National Assembly (central) and elected People's Councils (local).

Implementation of grassroots democracy: The people directly involved in the settlement of some hot issues in facilities such as land, housing, transportation... through meetings to discuss local or solicit comments, the vote of confidence for elected representatives, consultative conference ...

3. Vietnam communist party -Establishment and development

3.1. Historical period before the establishment of the Vietnam Communist Party

Vietnam the French colonial period, movements and political parties struggle for national liberation under the feudal tendencies and powerful bourgeois place. These movements and parties typically take place during this period are: Can Vuong Movement 1885 - 1896, uprisings occurred in Yen The 1884 - 1913 and established parties: the Constitutional Party (1925); Youth Party (1926); high expectations Youth Party (1926), and Vietnam that union (1925) ... The political parties of this period have contributed to promoting patriotic movements, especially the Vietnamese New Revolutionary Party and National Party of Vietnam. Vietnamese New Revolutionary Party and was born with a tendency to operate as the revolutionary proletariat. Vietnam National Party is a political party-oriented bourgeois democracy.

The objective of the struggle this period towards independence for the nation, but in the stance of the different political parties to restore feudalism, or setting up a constitutional monarchy, or higher as an established bourgeois republican regime.

3.2. Characteristics of the current status of the dominant party system in Vietnam

Communist Party of Vietnam was founded from the combination of Marxism - Leninism with the workers' movements and nationalist movements

The early twentieth century, society has made Vietnam a large change; two new classes are born working class and bourgeoisie. State moved from feudalism to colonial semi-feudal. There are two Social fundamental contradictions exist between all our people with the French colonialists invaded and among working people with the feudal landlord class lackeys. Nguyen Ai Quoc was the founder of the Communist Party of Vietnam has been receiving ideological Marxist - Leninism applied in practice in Vietnam, which is the harmonious combination between the nation and era.

The development of the revolutionary movement requires political party leaders. So at the end of the year's 20th century, the communist organization was established. June -1929, the Indochinese Communist Party founded in the Northern States. In 1929, Annam Communist Party was established in the Southern States. In 1930, the Indochinese Communist League was founded in the Middle States.

The impact of the Russian October Revolution and the Communist International

Russian October Revolution and the Comintern strong vote movement of the working class, people of other countries and is one of the driving force behind the birth much like the Communist Party: Communist Party of France, Communist Party of China...

The consolidation of communist organizations founded the Vietnam Communist Party

Three communist organizations active isolation is the risk to divide the worker's movement, the revolutionary movement for national liberation. So, in February 1930, leader Nguyen Ai Quoc Party organizations merged three took the name Communist Party of Vietnam. This is a major milestone, a great turning point in the history of Vietnam's revolution.

The leadership of the Communist Party of Vietnam in the period

From 1930 to now, the Communist Party of Vietnam has organized and led the implementation of all social victory of the people of Vietnam.

August 1945, led the Communist Party of the People's Revolution successful termination of the colonial yoke of French colonialism, set up the Vietnam Democratic Republic. It was the first State of Democratic People in South East Asia. Turn the people of Vietnam era of independence, freedom, democracy.

In 1954, after nine years leading the war against invading French victory, the Party has won control over half of the country of Vietnam. During this period the political system of Vietnam is a democratic political system the people. Based on the foundation of the great national unity is very broad: regardless of race, class, religion, ideology, doctrine, not class struggle policy. Put the interests of the nation is the highest.

From 1954 to 1975, the Communist Party has led the construction of new regimes in the North, made revolutionary people's democratic nation in the South, the resistance against U.S. aggression and liberate the country Southern completely in 1975, unifying the country.

From 1975 to 1986, by the maintenance mechanism of centralized bureaucratic management, subsidies to the state apparatus cumbersome and inefficient; the elected bodies at all levels are chosen, voting and running as Republic forms

Since 1986, the Communist Party has initiated and led with "**Renovation**" to look at the spiritual truth, to appreciate the truth, tell the truth. Party has set out a comprehensive renovation, including the transition from a planned economy to focus, bureaucracy, subsidies to the market economy socialist orientation. After 30 years of renovation, Vietnam has made great achievements and historical significance. It is shown on both sides: the achievements in practice and in perception.

In practice, Vietnam has been out of the economic crisis - social, change the basic and comprehensive. Rapid economic growth, the industrialization, modernization, economic development-oriented market socialism was strengthened. People's lives improved significantly. The political system and the great national unity to be consolidated and strengthened political-social stability, national defense, and security are maintained the position of Vietnam in the international arena constantly improving. The combined strength of the country has greatly increased, creating a new position and power to the country continue to come up with good prospects.

In theory, the Party was more aware of socialism and the path towards socialism. A reasoning systems perspective on reform, the socialist society and their upward socialism in Vietnam have been formed on the basics.

These achievements demonstrate that the renewal of the Party is correct, creative, and consistent with practices in Vietnam. However, the Party was also present, fields are weak, sometimes make mistakes, mistakes. It is important that the Party soon discover weaknesses and mistakes, their weaknesses, work out proper measures to correct and timely. Party self-criticism publicly, before people get mistakes and correct results.

To perform its mission leaders, the Communist Party of Vietnam to his regular self-regulating it as a rule for survival and development of the Party. Party to respect and listen to the people to plan policy, guidelines, and policies. Party oriented rather than doing the work of the State.

3.3. The main features of the formation of the current political regime in Vietnam

Firstly, the political regime of Vietnam is a political party can only govern. Party leaders of the political system, and is part of the system of politics. The political system in Vietnam is one of the political institutions, does not exist in opposition political parties.

Secondly, all political systems are organized and operated on the basis of ideology is Marxism - Leninism and Ho Chi Minh.

Thirdly, highlights the political system of Vietnam is a political system to represent many classes, social strata. Classes, social strata are represented by the member organizations in the political system, both acknowledged the leadership role of the working class. Therefore, our country's political system of our country is deeply belonging to working-class people by nature.

Fourthly, the state socialist Republic of Vietnam is a state of the people, by the people, for the people. National independence associated with socialism has been linked with ethnic issues matter the class, creating a synergy of the entire political system.

Fifthly, to improve the way the Party's leadership over the activities of the political system, implementing the principle of democratic centralism; the exercise of democracy within the Party and in society, to accelerate decentralization and strengthening regime personal responsibility, especially the individual heads.

Sixthly, the Democratic Party is in a critical review and a frank and constructive especially those issues that are facing the Party and people are suffering. In 2010, the first time, Communist Party policy for a pilot implementation of the general assembly directly elected secretary. There is about 15-20% pilot province directly elected congress secretary, even directly elected Secretary. The purpose of the pilot directly elected congress secretary is to continue to expand direct democracy within the Party, promoting the direct democracy of the party congress delegates of all levels, anti-democratic forms of expression, radical democracy, local ideology, factionalism. From the model of party leadership election in a democracy, openness and transparency will also have a profound impact on the general election, elections throughout Vietnam.

4. Election system in Vietnam

4.1. Current electoral system in Vietnam

Election activities and the country's leadership are two activities closely related to each other, faithfully reflect the political situation as well as leadership capacity in each country. An election is considered to be successful in ensuring free and fair democracy really contributes to building genuine democracy, enrich cultural and political achievements of a country.

Vietnam is a country single, unified under the leadership and only the Communist Party of Vietnam. Currently, the dominant system of elections in Vietnam now is a majority regime to comply with four principles: universal, equal, direct and secret ballot. State of Vietnam ensures the right to vote and stand for election of people as the basic freedoms of citizens. The people elect the National Assembly, while the higher level is the National Assembly elected the form of representative democracy. It is a question of principles, are recognized in all the Constitution, the Election Law of the National Assembly Election Law Council of People's Deputies.

In the system of organs of State power, the National Assembly of Vietnam is the agency the highest state power, is the supreme representative organ of the people. That was the most representative organization for people's ownership in the selection of national leaders, chosen to represent the will of the people who represent the people through which to perform power their own. After the revolution succeeded in August 1945, people voted on the first National Assembly on 01.06.1946. Currently, the 12th National Assembly, followed in 2011 will proceed to the election of deputies to the National Assembly 13.

Also in the form of elections, at local, people elected People's Councils. People's Council is an institution representing the people of an administrative-territorial, on behalf of local people decides on matters concerning local needs come from, people's lives locally. Structure, composition candidates are based on the results of the three-round Consultative Conference at both central and provincial level. How are the vote on the election list and the election units? A number of candidates at least two people more than the number of deputies elected in each electoral unit to facilitate the choice of voters. Among the delegates that the election units to be elected, candidates are more than half the valid votes and the most votes are elected. In many cases the votes are equal, older people are elected.

4.2. Strengths of the electoral system applied in Vietnam

Election system in Vietnam with the way the organization has been mentioned above has shown clear superiority in the face, such as:

Firstly, the provisions on the election have shown clearly and fully in the Constitution and the laws related to elections (mentioned above), specifically: Standards and Standards of voters who Delegates participating candidates, funding elections, in voting activity is controlled by the Election Commission inspection ... The provisions of the law on *the standard participants delegate candidates* on the principle of respect for the right candidate participation of citizens, without distinction between those who presented themselves participating candidate or candidates. In Vietnam, funding *elections of deputies* to the National People's Assembly and the state budget, the self-nominated candidates should not put the money or any escrow funds. The organization works with election regulations in each region to vote is 300 to 2000 voters (depending on regions) to easily organize the vote and vote count. There are regulations announced the election units (previous 90 days), the list of candidate units (previous 70 days) people have enough time to study and learn about the candidates and can send single report, no confidence for the candidate that they believe is not qualified.

Secondly, the propaganda about the election in Vietnam should be a very good turnout rate reached a very high rate. Before Election Day, the body mass media actively report on election events and encourage all people to participate and just exercising their duties.

Thirdly, The role of Fatherland Front of Vietnam is very important in organizing consultations. Consultative general election to meet with the intellectual common ground is not high and there is limited information, this step allows organizations and representatives of the people who choose to participate preliminary candidates selected before the people, thereby improving the quality of candidates, as the link between voters and candidates who participated by organizing for candidates who participate in contact with voters, advocacy organizations, election campaigning.

Fourthly, The election's system is quite simple and conformity with the educational level of the majority of citizens. So there is always an election result, not the situation that must re-election on time wasters as well as funding and no votes were scattered.

Fifthly, contains provisions on the structure and reasonable rates for components of the field representatives, have the structure of regional ... create a diversity of participants. Besides the participants are working at the State agencies, armed forces, the Fatherland Front and mass organizations, there is an appropriate proportion of deputies of ethnic minorities, religions, of women, participants are scientists, intellectuals, business people typical of all economic sectors. According to the XII National Assembly, has 493 deputies, with 473 people (95.94% have a university degree, representatives of ethnic minorities compared to 87 people (accounting for 17.65%), female delegates 127 people (25.76%), young (under 40) have 68 people (13.79%) in the youngest participants born in 1983, delegates are not party members who have 43 (8.72%), religions 14 people (2.84%), self-nominated 1 person (0.2%).

4.3. The existence of the electoral system in Vietnam

Besides the outstanding strengths of the electoral system in Vietnam, before the challenges of the innovation process of democracy and globalization, the electoral system in Vietnam is facing some problems inadequacies need to overcome.

First representatives of standards, if only based on 5 criteria were defined is unclear, it should more clearly define the level of culture, certain operations, new candidates, has thus improved the quality of new activities of participants in particular and activities of the National Assembly in general. The compositional structure of deputies, besides the positive aspects mentioned above, the main structure defining quality that also creates uneven delegates, delegates are not professional activities, usually, only one active Key had barely acquainted with the work of the school then was not structured in the following term. So the choice candidate should have specific plans for each grade as planning ahead Games delegates (delegates by ownership structure), medium-term planning (deputies in charge) and long (university professional expression).

Secondly, on the opinions of voters are still *inadequate*. Voters must take the comments of voters where candidates work and residence, but now a host to a type, not system most organizations have a place in the form of the secret ballot, where the organization is in the form of hands. Soon will be amended Election Law on Organization of a consistent form of secret ballot vote of confidence after each response appointed members.

Thirdly, the distribution of candidates in the Central Local candidates is difficult to sort. Currently, the Council sent to the Election Committee election candidates list central, often the candidate will be a delegate in charge of operations in central introduced the local candidates, candidates may wish to note two local candidates (usually the candidates in

the central northern provinces usually chosen for convenience of operation, it is difficult allocation). Need to define specific criteria for allocation of candidates on the central provinces.

Fourthly, There are few self-selected candidates. In recent years, the number of participants self-nominated candidates has increased substantially. According to data election 12th National Assembly, the number of candidates is 231 persons themselves, but when the third round negotiation was left with only 30 people, by the number of candidates is not meeting the standards, not great Interface for interest groups, not paying attention to the open records ... A number of candidates elected only one person. This shows that the number of self-nominated candidate for this unknown power of centralized collective interests of a group, organization or professional associations ... to attract votes for himself.

Fifthly, the deputy's part-time status is so common. There are a number of delegates too much work part-time basis, positions should not have enough time and health to perform the tasks that their representatives in accordance in Law the deputies must spend at least 1 / 3 to serve time for the work of Congress.

Sixthly, between the candidates, there is no significant *competition*. The candidates when the candidates need to offer programs of concrete action when elected. Because there is no competition between candidates, many candidates as the election are the work assignment. Therefore, the candidates have not really focused on hone presentation skills, campaign skills, contacts and convince voters that they still have the ability to win. That dilemma has led to these new factors can be washed into the political system, making diversification object delegates.

Seventhly, the current status of the election of deputies to People's Councils at all levels: previously, the People's Council has three levels: provincial, district and commune. But in the current period of innovation and in the course of operation, the role of communal People's Council district where the longer form, not really promote the role of people's representatives at local and intermediate levels is caused delays for law enforcement at the local before deciding to implement local policies. Currently, Vietnam is a pilot remove Council of districts and communes in 10 provinces and cities across the country and also direct the pilot elected Secretary cum Chairman of districts and communes in some localities.

Lastly, people participate in the election also brought formality. Many people do not see the vote biography, list of candidates. That affects the quality of delegates and that is the lack of civic consciousness in the selection of deserving candidates to represent them.

The referral decision and select the most worthy representatives to the supreme power body of people who cannot make the most accurate and fair by the people.

5. Discussion

Vietnam's position on the international stage has been confirmed in the country. Achievements Vietnam has made in over 30 years of innovation as contributions by the entire Party and people.

The participation of Vietnamese Citizens is playing a very important role in those contributions to the enormous strength of the great national unity.

Facing the challenges of democracy and globalization issues, our Party has always focused direction and put the right policy leadership of the State exercising the right to equality for all people and the power to mobilize the entire population by increasingly boosted people's ownership, respect people's participation in all aspects and all sectors of society towards a democratic society, justice and civilization. /.

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